

SUPER MOONS, COVID-19, AND QURAN: FINAL OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Statistics of the Covid-19 pandemic show unique coincidences of prominent pandemic events with Super Moon occurrences. Although no causal relation can be suggested for these coincidences, they are interesting insofar as they may be linked to possible futuristic messages embedded in the Quran. Newly observed Super Moon coincidences, along with those observed before, could further support a pandemic perspective for chapter 74 in the Quran. This article presents the final observations related to this general topic and is complementary to the two other articles published before.

Keywords: Super Moons, Covid-19, Pandemic, Quran

1. Introduction

Moon's orbit around the Earth is not circular and Earth-Moon distance shows periodic variations. When a Full Moon appears in its closest distance from the Earth, it is called a **Super Full Moon (SF)**, and when a New Moon is in its closest distance from the Earth, it is called a **Super New Moon (SN)** [1]. Fig.1 shows computed Earth-Moon distance and Super Moons of the years 2020 through 2023 [2]. According to a rather stringent criterion, any Earth-Moon distance less than 360,000-km (within the blue area in Fig.1) indicates occurrence of a Super Moon [1].

Fig.1 Computed Earth-Moon distance, Super Moons, and their given acronyms

Computed dates for observing these Super Moons with their phases [3], and their given acronyms are shown in Table.1 and specified in Fig.1. As can be seen from Fig.1 (or Table.1), from 2020 to 2023, each year has two Full and two New Super Moons.

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Table.1 Occurrence dates, phases, and acronyms of the Super Moons from 2020 through 2023

Date of Occurrence	Phase of the Super Moon	Acronym
March 9 2020	Full	SF1(0)
April 7-8 2020	Full	SF2(0)
October 16 2020	New	SN1(0)
November 15 2020	New	SN2(0)
April 27 2021	Full	SF1(1)
May 26 2021	Full	SF2(1)
November 4 2021	New	SN1(1)
December 4 2021	New	SN2(1)
January 2 2022	New	SN1(2)
June 14 2022	Full	SF1(2)
July 13 2022	Full	SF2(2)
December 23 2022	New	SN2(2)
January 21 2023	New	SN1(3)
February 20 2023	New	SN2(3)
August 1 2023	Full	SF1(3)
August 31 2023	Full	SF2(3)

Recently, chapter 74 of the Quran has been suspected to contain coded futuristic messages about the Covid-19 pandemic and the Spanish flu of 1918 [4,5]. In particular, verse 74:32, which is a swearing to the Moon, is suspected to be referring to the observed coincidences of Super Moons with major pandemic events [4]. In the last few months pandemic seems to have subsided into its endemic stage, making study of its full-course events possible. In this article, after presenting prominent Super Moon coincidences, their possible Quranic relevance will be discussed.

2. Prominent Super Moon Coincidences of the Covid-19 Pandemic

A prominent point observed in any of the graphical statistics of the pandemic, be it a turning point, an uprising, a maximum, or a minimum, can be considered as a pandemic event. The most prominent event coincidences in the course of the Covid-19 pandemic, including those reported before [4], will be shown here. Worldometer graphical statistics [6] of both, “Fatalities” and “Cases”, will be used to show these Super Moon coincidences.

2.1 Fatality Statistics

Fatality Statistics are probably the most accurate of all pandemic statistics because, number of deaths is the least likely to have been miscounted. Among these, “Daily Deaths” (Fig.2) shows outstanding coincidences, such that, each and every one of the first Super Full Moons of 2020 to 2023, without exception, shows coincidence with a prominent point in its statistics.

Fig.2 Major events and coincidences of “Daily Deaths” with, **SF1(0)**, **SF1(1)**, **SF1(2)**, and **SF1(3)**

“**Total Deaths**” in logarithmic scale (Fig.3) shows 3 turning points as the only features in entirety of its plot. Two of these turning points coincide with the occurrence dates of the first and the second Super Full Moons of the year 2020, **SF1(0)** and **SF2(0)**, respectively.

Fig.3: “Total Deaths” in logarithmic scale shows unique coincidences with **SF1(0)** and **SF2(0)**

“**Total Deaths**” in linear scale (Fig.4) shows three turning points as the only major features in the entirety of the plot. The middle one of these three points, coincides exactly with the occurrence date of the second New Moon of 2020, **SN2(0)**.

Fig.4 “Total Deaths” in linear scale shows a distinct slope increase which coincides with **SN2(0)**

Fig.5 “Outcome of total closed cases” showing unique coincidences with **SF1(0)** and **SF2(0)**

Graphs of “Outcome of total closed cases” (Fig.5) show coincidences of their only two features, one minimum and one maximum, with the occurrence dates of the first and the second Super Full Moons of 2020, SF1(0) and SF2(0), respectively.

2.2 Case Statistics

“**Total Cases**” in logarithmic scale (Fig.6), like its counterpart in “Total Deaths”, shows 3 turning points as the only notable features in the entirety of its plot. Two of these turning points coincide with the occurrence dates of the first and the second Super Full Moons of the year 2020, **SF1(0)** and **SF2(0)**, respectively.

Fig.6 “Total Cases” in logarithmic scale showing its coincidences with **SF1(0)** and **SF2(0)**

“**Total Cases**”, in linear scale too, shows a very unique and prominent Super Moon coincidence (Fig.7). The second, and in fact, the sharpest uprise in this graph appears as a unique upward turning point that takes place around January the 2nd, 2022. This date coincides exactly with occurrence date of the first Super New Moon of 2022, **SN1(2)**.

The sudden surge observed in “Total Cases” plot which coincides with **SN1(2)**, corresponds to the explosion of case numbers due to emergence of the Omicron variant of the Covid-19 pandemic which happened in the early January of 2022.

Fig.7 “Total Cases”, showing coincidence of the Omicron explosion of the cases with SN1(2)

3. Discussion

3.1 Super Moon coincidences

“Daily Deaths” statistics, all by itself, shows the most orderly and inclusive of all Super Moon coincidences in Covid-19 pandemic. Fig.2 is quite illustrative in this respect, where simultaneity of every year’s first Super Full Moon with a salient point in the mortality statistics can clearly be observed. *The first Super Full Moon of each and every consecutive year from 2020 to 2023, without exception, coincides with a prominent event in the Daily Deaths statistics:*

The first Super Full Moon of 2020, SF1(0), occurs on **March 9th 2020** which coincides with the first major surge in daily deaths. Although fatalities have started earlier, the clear eruption in the number of deaths starts on this date.

The first Super Full Moon of 2021, SF1(1), occurs on **April 27th 2021** which coincides with a prominent central peak in the daily mortalities.

The first Super Full Moon of 2022, SF1(2), occurs on **June 14th 2022** which coincides exactly with a distinct minimum which marks the greatest drop in daily mortalities ever observed in the course of the pandemic. In spite of it being followed by two relatively short peaks, this prominent minimum also appears to be setting the stage for the endemic state of the pandemic.

The first Super Full Moon of 2023, SF1(3), occurs on **August 1st 2023** which coincides with termination of a long, low-slope, linear drop in daily mortalities, a termination that marks start of a true endemic. From here on, global daily mortalities seem to level off, somewhere around 250 deaths/day.

It is interesting to observe from Fig.2, that the whole range of “Daily Deaths” statistics, from the start of the pandemic in March of 2020 to the start of the endemic in July of 2023, is almost exactly constrained between the first Super Full Moons of 2020 and 2023, **SF1(0)** and **SF1(3)**.

“Total Deaths” and “Total Cases” (Fig.3 and Fig.6), each have only 3 turning points in the entirety of their logarithmic plot and 2 of these 3 points coincide with occurrence dates of the only two Super Full Moons of 2020. As can be seen from Fig.4 and Fig.7, these two statistics do not show any proportionality in their linear plots, therefore, similarities of their statistics and coincidences in logarithmic presentations should not be considered as expectable.

In Fig.4 “Total Deaths” in its linear plot shows a major upward turn in the first year of the pandemic which coincides exactly with a Super New Moon, **SN2(0)**. This Super Moon coincidence is unique and exclusive to this, and to no other pandemic statistics.

“Outcome of total closed cases” (Fig.5) shows only two features in the form of a maximum and a minimum in the entirety of its plots, and again, these two extremums coincide with the only two Super Full Moons of the year 2020.

Finally, “Total Cases” in its linear plot (Fig.7) shows a unique and prominent uprise which is due to the Omicron explosion of the cases and coincides exactly with **SN1(2)**, a Super New Moon in 2022. This Super Moon coincidence is also unique and is exclusive to this plot.

It can be seen from Fig.1, that, almost half of the Super Moons observed during the course of the pandemic (5 Super Full Moons and 2 Super New Moons) show unique and independent coincidences with prominent pandemic events. Statistically speaking, this number of independent coincidences may be considered as highly improbable, particularly since no causal relation could be found for their happenings [4]. The question now is, can all these independent and unique coincidences be happening out of chance, or could it be that, pandemic events have been somehow coordinated to be in phase with Super Moon occurrences?

3.2 Quranic relevance

Chapter 74, which chronologically is one the first Quranic revelations, has recently been suspected of containing prophetic messages about the Covid-19 pandemic [4,5]. In this view, which is based on certain observations, the number 19 mentioned in verse 74:30 is suggested to be referring to the “19” in labeling of the Corona virus. An extensive account of this perspective has been given before, where a linkage to the Spanish flu of 1918 has also been mentioned [4].

The central theme of chapter 74, titled “The Cloaked one”, is description of a denier through verses 12-15 as being a wealthy man with many heirs, enjoying a life of comfort and power and yet, greedily wanting more. However, since he rejects signs of God and because of his wrongdoings, a divine reprisal is promised to him which is specified by a number “19” on it (74:30). Of course, traits of such an individual can also be extended to societies, in fact, from verse 31 on, tone of the verses appears to change to plural.

Verse 74:31 points to a common certainty that will be conceded by Christians, Jews and believers (Muslims) alike. From the pandemic perspective, the subject of this certainty has been suggested to be the observed imbalances in Covid-19 relative fatalities of the three Abrahamic religion populations [7]. Verses 32-37, follow as [8]:

74:32 *Nay, by the Moon*

74:33 and by the night when it departs

74:34 and by the dawn when it brightens

74:35 It is one of the mightiest things

74:36 A warning to mankind

74:37 For anyone of you who wishes to advance or lag behind!

During the development of the pandemic, it was noticed that Super Moons frequently show coincidences with major pandemic events [4]. These observations seemed to hint at possibility of connection between the swearing to the Moon in verse 32, and Super Moon coincidences actually observed during the Covid-19 pandemic. This speculation also seemed to be in harmony with the general pandemic theme suspected for chapter 74. The Moon oath in verse 32 was therefore interpreted as a Quranic allusion to the Super Moon coincidences of the Covid-19 pandemic [4]. In this scenario, Super Moons play role of “hour markers of a celestial clock” to which major events of the pandemic have been tuned.

Verse 74:35 points to the severity of the promised reprisal and verse 74:36, consistent with a plural tone, describes it as a warning to all mankind. Verse 74:37 refers to a critical point in time, when mankind will have to make a crucial decision to “advance or lag behind”. Verses 74:43-46, together with some earlier verses, describe types of conduct that make the divine reprisal deserved, such as, nonbelief, greed, and disregard for the needy humans. It is also notable that “warning to mankind”, perhaps to indicate importance of the matter, have been repeated two times in verses 74:31, and 74:36.

4. Conclusion

Additional coincidences of major pandemic events with Super Moon occurrences have been shown in this article, which along with other coincidences and explanations presented before [4, 7], can further strengthen a pandemic perspective for chapter 74 in the Quran. In particular, linkage between the Moon swearing verse 74:32 and the observed coincidences seems more plausible now. From the pandemic perspective of chapter 74, Super Moons may be acting as “hour markers of a celestial clock” according to which pandemic events have been supernaturally coordinated. In this scenario, Moon as a celestial witness, testifies on behalf of authenticity of the Quran, divine control of the pandemic events and, importance of a warning message aimed at future humans.

Today, perhaps more than ever before, world is facing great challenges of different types that can be detrimental to the fate of humans and even life on earth. If Super Moons have acted as markers of a pandemic clock, pandemic itself could be acting as marker of a momentous time in history. Covid-19 pandemic may then be significant, not only for the consequences directly associated with it, but also for the prominent events surrounding and shortly following it. This can make Covid-19 pandemic a historical landmark, deserving it to be called, as is stated in 74:36, “A mighty event”. Mankind at this stage will have the opportunity to correct wrong practices of the past and “advance” forward to a brighter future for all.

Appendix

Full and New Moons in the Quran

As a necessary condition, in order to be a Super Moon, the Moon must be in its Full or New phase. There are indications found in the Quran itself, that the Moon mentioned in 74:32 most probably should be in Full or New phase, and therefore can potentially be a Super Moon.

There are only two other verses in the Quran where Moon has been sworn to, 84:18 and 91:2, and phases of the Moon in these two verses are “Full” and “New”, respectively [4].

The swearing verses 74:33 and 74:34, which follow the Moon oath 74:32, could also be hinting at the Full and New phases of the Moon. This is because the Full Moon rises at sunset and can be seen in the *night sky*. On the other hand, a New Moon rises at sunrise with the sun and moves across the *day sky* with the sun [9]. So, swearing to the night and day which immediately follows the Moon oath in 74:32, can also be implying the Fullness and Newness of the Moon, respectively.

It is also interesting to note that, since most of the observed Super Moon coincidences in the Covid-19 pandemic correspond to the Full Moon, prioritization in ordering of the swearing verses, 74:33 (night) and 74:34 (day), can seem justified in this respect.

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